

Structure and Synthesis of Mukoline and Mukolidine, Two New Carbazole Alkaloids from *Murraya koenigii* Spreng.

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Mukoline and mukolidine, two new carbazole alkaloids from *Murraya koenigii* Spreng., have been assigned the structures 6-hydroxy-methyl-1-methoxy carbazole and 6-formyl-1-methoxy carbazole, respectively.

IN continuation of our interest in the carbazole alkaloids of the genus *Murraya*¹, we now report two minor alkaloids of C-13 skeleton isolated from the benzene extract of the roots of *Murraya koenigii* Spreng. The first compound, C₁₄H₁₃NO₂, mukoline (I), m.p. 115-20°, was optically inactive and gave a red picrate, m.p. 230°. The uv spectrum of I [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 221 (4.60), 242 (4.85), 252 (4.65), 258 (4.0), 280 (3.4), 290 (3.6), 320 (3.0) nm] suggested the presence of a 1-methoxy carbazole chromophore in it. The ir spectrum showed the presence of a hydroxyl group, NH-function and aromatic residue [ν_{max}^{KBr} 3440, 3240, 1610 cm⁻¹]. The nmr spectrum of mukoline (in CDCl₃) indicated the presence of NH-function (δ 8.22), aromatic protons (δ 7.0-7.9), deshielded benzylic methylene protons (δ 4.75), a hydroxyl proton (δ 4.45), aromatic methoxy protons (δ 3.9) and the meta-coupled aromatic proton at C-5 (J=2 cps).

The mass spectrum of I showed a molecular ion peak at m/e 227 and other significant peaks were at m/e 212 (M-15), 196 (M-31), 154 (M-15-31-28). The peak at m/e 154 could be represented by the ionic species (II) previously reported from glycozoline² and mukonine³.

Mukoline (I) on methylation with K₂CO₃ in acetone furnished the N-methyl derivative C₁₅H₁₅NO₂, m.p. 140° the uv spectrum of which was very similar to that of 1-methoxy carbazole. On acetylation, mukoline (I) gave an *o*-acetate (III) C₁₆H₁₇NO₃, m.p. 145° [M⁺ 269] ν_{max} 1720 cm⁻¹. The uv spectrum of the acetate was similar to that of I showing that the hydroxyl group was in the side chain. These data together with the nmr spectral data of I were suggestive of the presence of a CH₂OH group on carbazole nucleus which was confirmed by oxidation of I to its formyl derivative (IV), C₁₄H₁₁NO₂, m.p. 152-55°, ν_{max} 1660 cm⁻¹, [M⁺ 225]. The uv spectrum of (IV) [λ_{max} 238 (4.74),

248 (4.46), 275 (4.82), 290 (4.48), 330 (4.34)] was very similar to that of 3-formyl carbazole but not super-imposable with murrayanine⁴ (V). It (IV) was also not identical with murrayanine (V) [m.p., m.m.p., tlc]. The aldehyde (IV) on decarbonylation furnished 1-methoxy carbazole [λ_{max} 241 (4.5), 286 (3.84), 320 (3.46)] confirming that IV is 1-methoxy-6-formyl carbazole. Therefore, mukoline could be formulated as 1-methoxy-6-hydroxy methyl carbazole. This was also substantiated by comparison of I with 1-methoxy-3-hydroxy methyl carbazole⁴, previously obtained by Na-borohydride reduction of murrayanine (V), when it was found that these two compounds were nonidentical.

Along with mukoline, another homogeneous, optically inactive carbazole alkaloid C₁₄H₁₁NO₂, m.p. 152-55°, [M⁺ 225] was obtained from the same plant. The compound, named mukolidine (IV), gave a 2,4-DNPH derivative. The ir spectrum of mukolidine showed the presence of a NH-function (3185 cm⁻¹), aldehyde function (1660 cm⁻¹) in an aromatic system. The uv spectrum of IV [λ_{max} 238, (4.74), 248 (4.46), 275 (4.82), 290 (4.48), 330 (4.34)]. was very similar to that of a 3-formyl carbazole.

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The nmr data of IV showed the presence of an aldehyde proton (δ 10.8, s, 1H), -NH- proton (δ 8.6, s, 1H), aromatic protons (δ 8.15, 8.08, 7.3-7.6) and an aromatic methoxy group (δ 4.05, s, 3H). The nmr data together with the mass spectral fragmentation [m/e 225, 210, 182, 167] showed it to be a 3 or 6 formyl carbazole with methoxy group in it. The position of the methoxyl group was determined by decarbonylation of IV when 1-methoxy carbazole was obtained. On borohydride reduction mukolidine (IV) furnished an alcohol identical with mukoline (I) (m.m.p., ir, uv). So, it appeared that mukolidine was 1-methoxy-6-formyl carbazole and was identified with the oxidation product of mukoline as detailed above (m.m.p., ir, uv). The conclusions were supported by synthesis below.

2-Hydroxy methylene cyclohexanone (VI) was reacted with toluene diazonium chloride (VII) under Japp-Klingemann conditions when 1,2-dione-1'-(4'-methyl) phenyl hydrazone (VIII), m.p. 205° was obtained. The hydrazone (VIII) on indolization with a mixture of acetic acid and hydrochloric acid furnished 6-methyl-1-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro carbazole (IX), m.p. 190° which on dehydrogenation with Pd/C at 180° gave a 6-methyl-1-hydroxy carbazole (X). On methylation with diazomethane, the hydroxy compound (X) gave a crystalline homogeneous methoxyderivative (XI), m.p. 150°. On oxidation with DDQ, the compound (XI) gave an aldehyde which was found to be identical with mukolidine (IV) by direct comparison. The synthetic mukolidine on reduction with sodium borohydride furnished the hydroxymethyl derivative, m.p. 115-20° which was found identical with mukoline (I). Thus the structures of (I) and (IV) were confirmed by synthesis.

The oxidative functional variants of C-methyl group at 3-position⁸ i.e., CHO, COOH, COOMe have been encountered in carbazole alkaloids. Mukoline provides the first example of the occurrence of hydroxymethyl group, an oxidative variant of CH₃ at 6-position of carbazole alkaloids. The hydroxymethyl group of mukoline (I) has been oxidised to CHO group in mukolidine (IV).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether used had the b.p. 60-80° unless otherwise mentioned. The alumina for column chromato-

graphy and the silica gel for thin layer chromatography were supplied by Sarabhai Chemicals of India.

Isolation of mukoline (I) and mukolidine (IV): Air dried finely powdered roots of *Murraya koenigii* Spreng. (1Kg) was soxhleted for 48 hr with benzene. The extract was concentrated and chromatographed over alumina. The petroleum ether extract on evaporation gave a solid residue which on recrystallisation from benzene yielded mukolidine, m.p. 152-55°. [Found: C, 74. ; H, 4.55, N, 6.06; O, 14.4. C₁₄H₁₁NO₂ requires C, 74.6; H, 4.8; N, 6.2; O, 14.2%]. It gave a 2,4-DNPH derivative melting at 300°.

The benzene, benzene-chloroform eluents from the same chromatographic column on evaporation gave an oily residue which on recrystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether furnished homogeneous crystals of mukoline, m.p. 115-20° which on recrystallisation melted at 118°. [Found: C, 73.85; H, 5.70; N, 6.15; C₁₄H₁₃NO₂ requires C, 74.0; H, 5.72; N, 6.16%]. It gave a picrate which on crystallisation from benzene melted at 230°.

N-methyl mukoline: A mixture of mukoline (25 mg) in dry acetone (12.5 ml), methyl iodide (0.5 ml) and potassium carbonate (250 mg) was refluxed for 6 hr. It was then filtered. On working up, the filtrate furnished crystals which after filtration and recrystallisation from benzene-pet. ether mixture gave a homogeneous compound, m.p. 140°. [Found: C, 74.5; H, 6.1; N, 5.6. C₁₅H₁₃NO₂ requires C, 74.6; H, 6.2; N, 5.7%].

Acetylation of mukoline: Mukoline (10 mg) in acetic anhydride (0.1 ml) was heated with sodium acetate on water bath for 6 hr. The reaction product on working up furnished crystals which on recrystallisation from benzene-pet. ether mixture melted at 145°. [Found: C, 78.65; H, 5.46; N, 5.15. C₁₆H₁₅NO₂ requires C, 78.80; H, 5.57; N, 5.20%].

Oxidation of mukoline with active MnO₂: Formation of the formyl derivative (IV): To a solution of mukoline (50 mg) in dry CCl₄ (30 ml), active MnO₂ (500 mg) was added. The mixture was stirred for 5 hr and filtered. The filtrate after removal of the solvent yielded a solid, m.p. 152-55° which on sublimation and recrystallisation from benzene-pet. ether mixture melted at 152-55°.

Decarbonylation of the oxidation product (IV), formation of 1-methoxy carbazole (V): The above oxidation product (40 mg) was mixed with Pd/C (20 mg) and heated in a vacuum sealed tube in presence of 1 ml of dry alcohol for 15 min at 270°. The reaction product was taken in benzene-pet. ether mixture and allowed to crystallize when 1-methoxy carbazole, m.p. 69-70° was obtained and identified by thin layer chromatography, uv and m.m.p. with an authentic 1-methoxy carbazole.

Na-borohydride reduction of mukolidine: Sodium borohydride (25 mg) was added in cold to a solution

of mukolidine (150 mg) in dry methanol (8 ml). The solution was kept at room temperature for 2 hr. On working up the reaction mixture, and crystallisation from benzene-chloroform mixture, homogeneous crystals, m.p. 115-20° were obtained. Identification of this reduction product with natural mukoline was established by comparison of m.m.p., uv and ir.

Preparation of cyclohexane-1,2-dione-1'-(4-methyl) phenyl hydrazone (VIII): To a solution of 2-formyl cyclohexanone (3.2 g), sodium acetate (5 g) in water was added and the mixture stirred. A diazotised solution of *p*-toluidine (3.0 g) at 0-5° was added to it gradually during 40 min. The precipitate (VIII) was filtered, washed and dried. It was crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture, m.p. 205°. [Found: C, 71.90; H, 7.21; N, 12.30. $C_{13}H_{16}N_2O$ requires C, 72.22; H, 7.40; N, 12.49%].

Preparation of 6-methyl-1-oxo-tetrahydro carbazole (IX): The above hydrazone (1.4 g) was added to boiling glacial acetic acid (13 ml). Conc. HCl (3.1 ml) was added to it through reflux condenser and the whole mixture was boiled for 3-4 min. The reaction product was poured into ice and stirred. The white crystals of the oxo-compound (IX) appeared which were filtered, washed and dried. It was recrystallized from benzene, m.p. 190°. [Found: C, 64.82; H, 6.51; N, 7.01. $C_{13}H_{15}NO$ requires C, 65.0; H, 6.53; N, 7.03%].

Preparation of 1-hydroxy-6-methyl carbazole (X): The above oxo-compound (75 mg) in dry alcohol (5 ml) was dehydrogenated at 250-70° for 4 hr in a sealed evacuated tube in presence of Pd-C catalyst (10%; 0.7 mg). The reaction product was then made free from catalyst and solvent and the oily residue taken in ether. The ether solution was extracted with 2% alkali. The alkali portion was taken, acidified and again extracted with ether. On removal of ether, the residue was taken in benzene, filtered through silica gel bed for purification. Finally, an oily mass was obtained on evaporation of the solvent.

Preparation of 1-methoxy-6-methyl carbazole (XI): The above hydroxy compound (X) in methanol was treated with an ethereal solution of diazomethane at 0-5° and the whole mixture was kept overnight in a refrigerator. After the removal of diazomethane and the solvent, the residue was taken in benzene and crystallised. The crystals were filtered, washed and dried, m.p. 150°. [Found: C, 79.70; H, 63.28; N, 6.42. $C_{14}H_{18}NO$ requires C, 79.59; H, 6.20; N, 6.63%].

Preparation of mukolidine (IV) by DDQ oxidation of 1-methoxy-6-methyl carbazole (XI): To a stirring solution of 1-methoxy-6-methyl carbazole (40 mg) in benzene, a solution of DDQ (20 mg) in dry benzene was added through a period of 15 min. The stirring was continued for 1/2 hr. The colour of the solution gradually changed from deep green to deep blue. The reaction product was then washed with 1% NaOH and extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed, dried and evaporated. The residue was taken in benzene and subjected to preparative thin layer chromatography in the solvent system $C_6H_6-CHCl_3$ (1:1). The spot, identical with natural mukolidine, was scraped out from the plate, taken in alcohol, warmed and filtered. The filtrate on evaporation gave a solid which on crystallization from benzene furnished homogeneous crystals, m.p. 152-55°, identical with mukolidine in all respects (uv, ir, m.p., m.m.p., R_f).

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References

1. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Fort. der Chem. Org. Natur.*, 1979, 34, 299.
2. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1966, 661.
3. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, P. BHATTACHARYYA, S. ROY, S. P. BHATTACHARYYA and A. K. BISWAS, *Phytochem.*, 1978, 17, 834.
4. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. K. BARMAN and P. K. BOSE, *Tetrahedron*, 1965, 21, 681.
5. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Planta Medica*, 1980, 59, 1929.